

A New Stereocontrolled Synthesis of (Z,Z)-3,13-Octadecadien-1-ol, (Z,Z)-3,13-Octadecadien-1-yl Acetate and their (E,Z)-Isomers

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Manuscript received 24 December 1991, accepted 17 February 1992

(Z,Z)-3,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (6)¹, a pheromone component of *A. apiformis* and its (E,Z)-isomer (7)², a sex pheromone of the popular twig clearing moth *Paranthrene tabaniformis* Rott. and (Z,Z)-3,13-octadecadien-1-yl acetate (8) and its (E,Z)-isomer (9) as sex pheromones³ of female lesser peach tree borer *Synanthedon pictipes* and female peach tree borer

Semi-hydrogenation⁹ of 5 using Lindlar's catalyst in n-hexane in the presence of quinoline gave the alcohol (6) which on acetylation furnished 8. However, 6 on LAH reduction in dry diglyme gave 7 followed by acetylation with Ac₂O/Py furnished pure 9. Spectral data of the compounds 6–9 were in close agreement with that reported in literature.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (a) $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{P}^+\text{Ph}_3\text{Br}^-$, NaNH_2 , HMPA/THF, -78° , (b) CBr_4 , PPh_3 , CH_2Cl_2 , (c) $n\text{-BuLi}$, $\equiv\text{C-OTHP}$, HMPA/THF, (d) PPTS, MeOH, 55° , (e) Lindlar's catalyst, n-hexane, quinoline, (f) dry diglyme, LAH, reflux, (g) Ac_2O , Py, CH_2Cl_2 .

Sanninoidea exitiosa have been identified. Literature records^{2,4} the syntheses of compounds 6–9. Herein, we report a simple synthesis of the title compounds (Scheme 1).

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-nonan-9-al (1) on Wittig reaction with the ylide of n-pentyltriphenyl phosphonium bromide⁵ (generated by using sodium amide as a base at -78°) gave 2. Treatment of 2 with $\text{CBr}_4/\text{PPh}_3$ in CH_2Cl_2 afforded 3. Alkylation of 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-3-butyne with 3 using $n\text{-BuLi}$ in THF/HMPA⁷ gave 4. Acid hydrolysis⁸ of 4 in methanol afforded 13-octadecen-3-yn-1-ol (5).

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel (ASC, Bombay) impregnated with CaSO_4 was used for tlc. Unless otherwise specified, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-tetradec-9(Z)-ene (2) : To

n-pentyltriphenyl phosphorane (prepared from 8.30 g, 20 mmol n-pentyltriphenyl phosphonium bromide and 0.078 g, 20 mmol sodamide in anhydrous 15 ml THF) was added HMPA (2 ml) and the mixture stirred for 90 min at room temperature. The deep orange coloured yield was then cooled at -78° and to it was added the aldehyde (1; 2.42 g, 10 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml), warmed to room temperature and stirred for another 5 h. The reaction mixture was then quenched with ice, extracted with n-hexane (50 ml), washed with brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography over silica gel afforded pure 2 (2.13 g, 72%) (Found: C, 76.88; H, 12.04. $C_{19}H_{36}O_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.02; H, 12.16%); ν_{\max} 3 075, 3 010, 2 950, 1 740, 1 645, 810 and 720 cm^{-1} (cis-double bond); δ (CCl_4) 0.85 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.2–1.6 (22H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.1–2.3 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.3–3.7 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2O$), 4.6 (1H, bs, 2-pyranyloxy-H-2) and 5.3–5.5 (2H, t, J 5.4 Hz, olefinic protons).

1-Bromo-tetradec-9(Z)-ene (3): Carbon tetrabromide (4.71 g, 14 mmol) was added to a solution of 2 (3.0 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (5 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere at room temperature. After stirring for 10 min, the mixture was cooled to 0° and triphenylphosphine (7.43 g, 28 mmol) was added in small portions, then stirred overnight at room temperature and filtered through silica gel. Evaporation of the solvent provided the bromide (2.48 g, 89%); ν_{\max} 2 900, 2 850, 1 640, 725 and 600 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.1–1.4 (16H, bs, saturated methylenes), 2.0–2.25 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.3–3.5 (2H, t, J 7.4 Hz, CH_2Br) and 5.25–5.55 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-octadeca-3-yn-13 (Z)-ene (4): A solution of n-BuLi (1.8 N; 2.0 ml) in n-hexane was added dropwise to a well-stirred and cooled solution of 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-3-butyne (0.56 g, 3.6 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) under N_2 -atmosphere at -10° for 30 min at the same temperature followed by dropwise addition of 3 (0.9 g, 3.3 mmol) in dry HMPA (2.5 ml). The stirring was continued for 3 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water, extracted with hexane, the organic solvent washed with water and dried. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure to furnish the product 4 (0.08 g, 71%); ν_{\max} 2 850, 1 650, 1 470, 1 140, 1 060 and 725 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.0 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3–1.4 (22H, bs, saturated methylenes), 1.85–2.5 (8H, m, allylic protons, $-H_2C-C\equiv C-$), 3.4–3.6 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2O$), 4.5 (1H, s, 2-pyranyloxy-H-2) and 5.2–5.6 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

13-(Z)-Octadecen-3-yn-1-ol (5): A mixture of p-toluene sulphonic acid (150 mg) and a solution of 4 (1.0 g, 2.9 mmol) in methanol (25 ml) was stirred for 4 h at 60° , the concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with 5%

NaHCO₃ solution (25 ml), followed by brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography over silica gel gave the product 5 (0.4 g, 57%) (Found: C, 81.69; H, 12.10. $C_{18}H_{32}O$ calcd. for: C, 81.81; H, 12.20%); ν_{\max} 3 400–3 300, 3 010, 2 860, 1 650, 1 470, 1 060 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3–1.4 (16H, bs, saturated methylenes), 1.8–2.3 (8H, m, allylic protons), 2.5 (1H, s, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 3.8 (2H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2O) and 5.3–5.6 (2H, t, olefinic protons).

(Z,Z)-3,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (6): Lindlar's catalyst (150 mg) and quinoline (2 drops) were added to a solution of 5 (1.0 g, 3.8 mmol) in dry n-hexane (50 ml). The mixture was shaken under hydrogen atmosphere. At the end of the uptake of 1 equiv. of hydrogen, the catalyst was filtered, the filtrate washed with water and dried. Evaporation of solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel gave 6 (0.9 g, 91%), b.p. $150-152^\circ/1\text{ mm}$ (Found: C, 81.08; H, 12.72. $C_{18}H_{34}O$ calcd. for: C, 81.20; H, 12.86%); ν_{\max} 3 350, 2 920, 1 660, 1 470, 1 050 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3–1.4 (16H, bs, saturated methylenes), 1.8–2.4 (8H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.2 (1H, s, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 3.5–3.6 (2H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2O) and 5.38–5.8 (4H, m, olefinic protons).

(E,Z)-3,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (7): To a vigorously stirred suspension of LAH (0.4 g, 10.5 mmol) in dry diglyme (50 ml), was added the alcohol (5; 0.8 g, 3.0 mmol) dropwise and the mixture was refluxed for 48 h. It was then diluted with ether (20 ml), poured into ice, acidified with 10% HCl, washed with 5% aqueous NaHCO₃ solution (20 ml), water and dried. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure to give the product 7 (0.5 g, 58%), b.p. $168-170^\circ/2\text{ mm}$ (Found: C, 80.08; H, 12.59. $C_{18}H_{34}O$ calcd. for: C, 81.20; H, 12.86%); ν_{\max} 3 500–3 450, 2 920, 1 650, 1 380, 1 050, 970 (*trans*-double bond) and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3–1.4 (16H, bs, saturated methylenes), 1.7–2.3 (4H, m, allylic protons), 3.0 (1H, s, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 3.5 (2H, t, CH_2O) and 5.2–5.8 (4H, m, olefinic protons).

(Z,Z)-3,13-Octadecadien-1-yl acetate (8) and (E,Z)-3,13-octadecadien-1-yl acetate (9): A mixture of 6 (1.2 g, 5 mmol) / 7 (1.2 g, 5 mmol) in dry methylene chloride, acetic anhydride (0.5 g, 5 mmol) and pyridine (0.53 g, 6.7 mmol) was stirred at room temperature for 5 h. The residue was then extracted with ether, dried followed by solvent evaporation and the residue chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) to give the products: 8 (1.14 g, 82%) (Found: C, 77.68; H, 11.90. $C_{20}H_{36}O_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.86; H, 11.76%); ν_{\max} 3 010, 2 940, 1 740, 1 660, 1 460, 1 370, 1 250, 1 040 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3–1.4 (16H, bs, saturated methylenes), 2.0 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.0–2.2 (8H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.9 (2H, t, CH_2O), 5.3–5.8 (4H, m, olefinic protons); 9 (1.1 g, 81%) (Found: C,

NOTES

77.72 ; H, 11.52. $C_{20}H_{36}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 77.86 ; H, 11.76% ; ν_{max} 2 940, 1 755, 1 660, 1 470, 1 370, 1 250, 1 040, 970 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3–1.4 (16 H, bs, saturated methylenes), 2.0 (3H, s, OCH_3), 1.8–2.2 (8H, m, allylic methylenes), 4.0 (2H, t, CH_2O) and 5.2–5.7 (4H, m, olefinic protons).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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